

Progress Towards a NIST Microwave Brightness Temperature Standard for Remote Sensing*

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Abstract— We discuss work at NIST aimed at developing a passive microwave brightness temperature standard. By reducing uncertainty, we can provide better calibrations for future weather and climate-monitoring radiometers. We discuss the calibration procedure used, measured data, and various theoretical and simulated results that have led to an improved understanding of the various uncertainty contributions in the measurement. We overview a Monte Carlo simulation to determine the uncertainty in target brightness temperature as a function of measurement distance and target size. We also discuss other future improvements including an improved blackbody design. The achievable calibration source brightness temperature uncertainty is expected to be reduced from the current 0.7 to 1.0 K from 18 to 65 GHz to less than 0.3 K.

Keywords—remote sensing; blackbody; passive microwave; calibration; traceability

I. INTRODUCTION

Passive microwave radiometers are used for remote sensing of the earth’s land, atmosphere, and oceans. Microwave measurements are used in satellite-and aircraft-mounted radiometers for numerical weather prediction and in innumerable other climate monitoring projects on both satellites and aircraft. NIST has developed a method to extend our standard waveguide radiometers to free space, allowing us to calibrate flight reference sources or ‘blackbodies’. This approach relies on the standard radiometer as the primary reference. We can also calibrate against a primary blackbody reference if available. The combination of both references creates a more robust calibration scheme and may reduce uncertainties.

The currently used hardware and measurement methods can provide a best-case calibration uncertainty of about ± 0.7 K. This level of uncertainty would be helpful for studying some environmental variables across different measurement platforms, but many long term climate variables require much smaller uncertainty in order to make significant scientific claims on a global scale. Recent work has involved simulation aimed at fully exploring the sources of uncertainty and identifying areas of potential improvement.

II. MEASUREMENT PROCEDURE

Free-space radiometric measurements are made in an anechoic chamber with the calibrated waveguide radiometer

flange (the reference plane for the measurements) attached to a horn antenna. The blackbody reference used for past measurements is an array of absorber-coated aluminum square pyramidal structures 40 mm in height with a base of 10 mm. Standard RF absorber is often made from pyramidal structures of carbon-loaded foam, but this target is manufactured with a 1 mm thick coating of high-quality iron loaded epoxy absorber. The absorber is cast onto the aluminum substrate material and an electronic resistance heater is attached to the backside of the aluminum. The target is designed to have a microwave emissivity of close to unity in order to most closely resemble an ideal blackbody. The passive blackbody radiance from the target, often referred to as “brightness temperature” (T_b), is directly related to the temperature of the target by Planck’s law. For a true blackbody, knowledge of the physical temperature is all that is needed to perfectly characterize its T_b . Temperature non-uniformity in the heated target will lead to measurement error because the analysis relies on a constant and uniform temperature distribution. When the horn views the blackbody there are some other considerations such as the target not completely filling the horn’s antenna power pattern. We quantify this with the illumination efficiency ratio. The measurement distance must also be carefully chosen to avoid coherence effects at close distances, while maintaining adequate signal strength and avoiding too much spillover from the background. The background temperature must be measured and is also assumed to be uniform. Determining the optimal measurement conditions is not trivial and requires some analytical and experimental investigation.

The relationship expressed in (1) describes how the brightness temperature of the target is calculated from a free-space radiometric measurement:

$$\bar{T}_{tg} = \frac{1}{\alpha\eta_{IE}} T_x - \frac{1}{\eta_{IE}} T_{bg}^{phy} - \frac{1}{\alpha\eta_{IE}} T_{ant}^{phy}, \quad (1)$$

where $\bar{T}_{tg}$ is the effective target brightness temperature, α is the antenna efficiency (related to ohmic loss), η_{IE} is the illumination efficiency, T_x is the brightness temperature measured at the waveguide flange of the radiometer, T_{bg}^{phy} is the physical temperature of the background, and T_{ant}^{phy} is the physical temperature of the antenna. The effective target brightness temperature is determined by integrating the product of the target’s physical temperature field, angular dependent

emissivity, and the power pattern of the antenna over the solid angle subtended by the target.

Fig. 1 shows the pyramidal array blackbody target mounted in the large NIST anechoic chamber with a standard gain horn mounted and aligned to take measurements of the target. Here, the target is exposed to the chamber environment. We have also made measurements using various types of insulation to reduce temperature gradients on the target surface, but this does slightly reduce the effective emissivity of the target.

Fig. 1. Measurement setup in the NIST anechoic chamber.

III. RESULTS

Fig. 2 presents the results of the calculated target brightness temperature versus measured physical temperature for measurements on the square pyramidal array target at 18 GHz. The error bars show the propagated uncertainty at each measurement distance. The full derivation for the uncertainty can be found in [1]. As the separation distance between the horn and the blackbody increases, the influence of the background increases because the target subtends a smaller solid angle fraction of the antenna pattern. The uncertainty in the background temperature is relatively high for this setup and dominates at larger distances. Research has been focused on reducing uncertainties in these measurements which would allow for a more robust and desirable standard.

The method described in [1] discusses the extraction of the illumination efficiency η_{IE} . The uncertainty in the illumination efficiency is correlated through a non-linear fitting to multiple radiometric data and the other physical temperatures in (1), so the overall calculated target brightness temperature uncertainty is difficult to express or predict analytically. A Monte Carlo simulation was performed to determine the uncertainty of the target brightness temperature as a function of measurement distance and blackbody size. Fig. 3 shows a contour of the Monte Carlo data. The illumination efficiency here is determined from a computer simulation result according to the method described in [2]. The plot shown is for 18 GHz. The plot is bounded at 0.5 K for improved resolution at lower uncertainty: the white area in the lower right is all > 0.5 K. The predicted total uncertainty is highly dependent on the systematic or type B uncertainty within the radiometer system.

An in-depth theoretical electromagnetics model was assembled to understand the effect of coherence on the black-

Fig. 2. Radiometrically derived target brightness temperature versus physical temperature at 18 GHz.

Fig. 3. Contour plot of Monte Carlo predicted target brightness temperature uncertainty (K).

Fig. 4. Result of coherence model showing normalized radiation magnitude versus distance for different blackbody radii (a).

body's radiation [3]. Fig. 4 shows the result of the electromagnetic analysis. When the blackbody target is located close to the radiometer front-end, the coherence effect of the blackbody radiation needs to be taken into account. There is a tradeoff between optimal blackbody size and measurement distance due to increased uncertainty at large distances and decreased normalized radiation at close distances resulting from coherence.

Current research at NIST involves the design of a blackbody that will optimize the measurement system and minimize measurement uncertainty. The blackbody will be a NIST primary standard intended for the calibration of customer radiometers. The typical square pyramidal arrays cover a small frequency range of optimal performance due to standing waves created by the pyramid absorbers. Alternative geometries such as single conical and wedge shaped cavities are being examined for use as a broader frequency laboratory standard. The proposed design will also greatly reduce uncertainty due to non-uniformity in the physical temperature distribution of the target.

The effective target brightness temperature is defined by the following integral:

$$\bar{T}_{tg} = \frac{\int_{target} T_{tg}(\theta, \varphi) \varepsilon(\theta, \varphi) F_n(\theta, \varphi) d\Omega}{\int_{target} F_n(\theta, \varphi) d\Omega}, \quad (2)$$

where T_{tg} is the physical temperature of the target, F_n is the normalized antenna power pattern, and ε is the target emissivity. The integral is evaluated in the spherical coordinate frame of the viewing antenna over the solid angle Ω subtended by the target. By minimizing the physical temperature gradients in the target and maximizing the emissivity, the angular dependence becomes negligible and the physical temperature can be removed from the integral. The method in [1] can then be used without need for the explicit antenna pattern data. The integral in (2) is evaluated for different blackbody variations and used as a performance metric for the design. The closer the effective brightness temperature is to the set temperature on the heated target, the better the performance of the blackbody.

Evaluation of (2) involves knowledge of the three variables in the integrand of the numerator. All three of these quantities are simulated with commercial software. The temperature field is simulated by means of commercial finite-element-method (FEM) computational fluid dynamics software. The full anechoic chamber is modeled in the software including the air circulation fans. The blackbody model is placed inside the chamber and the heater surface is defined as a constant temperature boundary condition. The steady-state temperature distribution on the absorber surface is solved for and saved. We determined that use of a 3 mm layer of closed-cell polyethylene foam insulation directly on the absorber surface greatly reduces the temperature gradients, but the effect on the emissivity must also be considered. Fig. 5 shows the conical blackbody temperature model inside the anechoic chamber, and fig. 6 shows an example of the resulting temperature distribution looking into the cone for the non-insulated target.

The emissivity distribution is determined from a commercial electromagnetic FEM software solution. We simulated the bidirectional reflectance distribution function (BRDF) which can be used to calculate the emissivity through reciprocity. Assuming that there is no transmittance through the aluminum-backed blackbody, the emissivity is calculated from,

$$\varepsilon(\theta, \varphi) = 1 - \int_0^\pi \int_0^{2\pi} r(\theta_r, \varphi_r, \theta, \varphi) \sin(\theta_r) d\theta_r d\varphi_r, \quad (3)$$

Fig. 5. Temperature model of conical blackbody set inside chamber.

Fig. 6. Resulting temperature distribution of absorber surface.

where r is the reflectance as a function of spherical incidence angles θ and φ and spherical reflected angles θ_r and φ_r . Fig. 7 shows the reflectance distribution for the insulated conical blackbody at 18 GHz and normal incidence excitation. The cone aperture is oriented downwards in the software so $\theta=180$ degrees refers to the view of the conical axis in the blackbody cavity.

The antenna power pattern is also simulated with the same electromagnetic FEM software, and for this case, we simulated a rectangular standard gain horn at 18 GHz.

We calculated the effective target brightness temperature in (2) for the open-air and insulated blackbody design cases. We chose to use an antenna-to-target separation distance of 40 cm for this analysis but this will be further optimized in future studies. The target heater was set to 350 K, as shown in fig. 6. The resulting effective target brightness temperature was 349.84 K and 349.995 K for the open-air and insulated cases,

Fig. 7. 18 GHz reflectance distribution for conical blackbody excited at normal incidence and 40 cm distance.

respectively. The application of the insulation layer greatly increases the agreement between the heater setting temperature and the effective target brightness temperature. This considerably reduces uncertainty in calibrations performed with the proposed blackbody.

IV. CONCLUSION

Through a combination of laboratory measurements, data analysis, theoretical derivation, and computational simulations we have been able to tune our measurement procedure to optimize the available hardware and understand the most beneficial improvements for uncertainty reduction.

Measurement distance is a critical parameter to optimize when measuring a blackbody in an anechoic chamber because of its effect on coherence, illumination efficiency, and emissivity.

A new blackbody design is in progress that will further reduce uncertainty in the calibration by optimizing the physical size of the body, reducing temperature gradients across the absorber, and maximizing the integrated emissivity. The measurements and simulations presented here aim to improve upon the NIST passive microwave brightness temperature standard and reduce uncertainties to levels required for long-term climate variable traceability. The results show that we will be able to reduce uncertainties in the 18 to 65 GHz frequency range from ± 0.7 K as seen in previous measurements to less than ± 0.3 K.

In the near future, we hope to calibrate the next-generation, operational, satellite-based microwave radiometer, called the Advanced Technology Microwave Sounder (ATMS) and, thus, begin the era of SI-traceable passive microwave climate data.

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